

Effect of sonication on the structure of hydrogenated amorphous carbon obtained through the pyrolysis of benzene

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Abstract : The interlayer spacing of hydrogenated amorphous carbon obtained through the pyrolysis of benzene, was found to change considerably on sonication (0.166 to 4.5 h) as observed from electron diffraction studies. The broadening of diffraction rings was found to change with sonication time, suggesting a continuous change in the degree of crystallinity. The electron micrographs also change from jumbled globular threads (on 0.166 h sonication) to discrete beady chains (on 4.5 h sonication). FTIR studies show that the $sp^3CH_2(sym)$ stretching mode at around 2850 cm^{-1} and the $sp^3CH_2(asym)$ stretching mode at around 2920 cm^{-1} are particularly sensitive to sonication. Upto 2 h sonication the concentration of $sp^3CH_2(sym)$ steadily rises and on further sonication its concentration gradually drops to an almost constant value. Plot of optical density (O.D.) at 2850 cm^{-1} as a function of sonication time shows a gaussian distribution. This property may be utilised to sense the ultrasonic waves and ascertain its dose.

Keywords : Sonication, pyrolytic carbon, electron diffraction.

With the discovery of fullerenes¹, carbon nano-tubes², carbon nano-wires³, interest on the microstructure of various forms of amorphous carbon has of late reached its pinnacle. Since amorphous carbons of various forms and various microstructures possess very special optical, mechanical and opto-electronic properties⁴, they continue to draw attention of material scientists. Microstructures of amorphous carbons derived through the dehydration of carbohydrates and carbon nano-rods in the sucrose carbon were observed⁵.

Graphite is known to change its structure from hexagonal to rhombohedral form on grinding⁶. Its cell parameters are exceedingly sensitive to the rise of temperature⁷. In this note we report that the interlayer spacing of hydrogenated amorphous carbon (a-C:H) derived through the pyrolysis of benzene changes considerably on sonication (0.166 to 4.5 h). We have tried simultaneously to understand the chemical changes involved in the process of sonication in terms of FTIR studies.

Results and discussion

Fig. 1 shows electron micrograph of 0.166 h, 2 h, 3 h and 4.5 h sonicated samples. In each micrograph, globular or beady threads characteristic of carbon network were observed. However, in case of 0.166 h sonicated sample tight-knit entangled network was observed. On further sonication the entanglement of the jumbled carbon network was loosened, giving rise to voids, whose radius increases with the sonication time. For example, on 2 h sonication voids of 50 nm radius

were observed and on 3 h sonication voids of 100 nm radius were formed. Fig. 1d i.e. micrographs of 4.5 h sonicated samples shows neither voids nor entangled threads, rather 500 nm long discrete globular chains (branched) made up of 50 nm radius beads.

Electron diffraction diagram of each sample essentially show two rings, one broad and another narrow ring, since short and intermediate orders are always found to be present in amorphous carbons. These rings were found to change their profile (broadening) and position on sonication. Table 1 depicts 'd' values (interlayer spacings) observed in the 0.166 h, 2 h, 3 h and 4.5 h sonicated samples. The extent of broadening also changes in a non-monotonic fashion, suggesting change in the degree of crystallinity in each phase of sonication. This is corroborated by FTIR studies as well.

Both unsonicated and 0.166 h sonicated sample shows, alongwith host of different bands, characteristic bands (stretching) of different hydrogen configurations :

$sp^3CH_2(sym)$, 2852 cm^{-1} ; $sp^3CH_2(asym)$, 2920 cm^{-1} ; sp^3CH , 2895 cm^{-1} very weak; $sp^2CH(aromatic)$, 3045 cm^{-1} weak; $sp^3CH_3(asym)$ 2963 cm^{-1} ; $sp^2CH_2(olef)$, 2994 cm^{-1} ; $sp^2CH(olef)$, 3016 cm^{-1} .

These bands were assigned as earlier⁸. All the above mentioned modes were found to change their integrated intensity and occasionally position on sonication. Fig. 2 shows the portion of FTIR spectra in the region of $2800\text{--}3000\text{ cm}^{-1}$

of the samples sonicated through different duration of time. A close inspection of FTIR spectra shows that on 2 h sonication the band assigned to $sp^2CH(arom)$ virtually disappears and so is the fate of $sp^2CH_2(olef)$ and $sp^2CH(olef)$ and at the same time (from Fig. 2) band assigned to $sp^3CH_2(sym)$ changes their intensity. The population of $sp^3CH_2(sym)$ steadily inflates upto 2 h sonication and then onwards gradually depletes, as observed from optical density measurement. A plot of O.D. of $sp^3CH_2(sym)$ band measured after linear background correction as a function of sonication time shows a gaussian distribution (Fig. 3)⁹.

Table 1. Change in interlayer spacing of benzene carbon with sonication time obtained from electron diffraction studies

Line no.	0.166 h sonicated sample	2 h sonicated sample	3 h sonicated sample	4.5 h sonicated sample
	L = 40 cm	L = 40 cm	L = 100 cm	L = 40 cm
	<i>d</i> (in Å)	<i>d</i> (in Å)	<i>d</i> (in Å)	<i>d</i> (in Å)
1	5.84131	2.856048	2.380040	3.30434
2	3.4312	1.999233	1.922340	2.00001

L = Length of the camera used, P = 200 kV, where P is applied voltage. $\lambda = 2.499042E - 2 \text{ \AA}$.

This property may be utilised to sense ultrasonic waves of 28 kHz and measure its dose.

Fig. 1. Electron micrograph of (a) 0.166 h, (b) 2 h, (c) 3 h and (d) 4.5 h sonicated hydrogenated amorphous carbon obtained through the pyrolysis of benzene.

It is extremely difficult to discern the presence of phenolic or alcoholic -OH using FTIR studies, since KBr pellets absorb moisture and the band due to -OH stretching of water engulfs

Fig. 2. FTIR spectra of (a) 0.166 h, (b) 2 h, (c) 3 h and (d) 4.5 h sonicated benzene carbon in the region of 2800–3000 cm^{-1} .

bands due to phenolic or alcoholic -OH stretching. But a band was observed at 1558 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of 0.166 h sonicated sample, which is assigned as hydrogen bonded carbonyl group attached to a conjugated system¹⁰. On further sonication this band becomes weaker (integrated intensity diminishes) and shifted towards higher wave number suggesting monotonic weakening of H-bonds¹¹. On 4.5 h sonication this band disappears suggesting complete rupture of H-bonds and discrete beady chains were observed in the micrograph at this stage, possibly as a sequel to rupturing of H-bonds.

FTIR spectrum of all the samples changes their sharpness on sonication suggesting change in the degree of crystallinity which corroborates our observation in electron diffraction studies.

Fig. 3. Plot of optical density $\times 10^3$ of the $sp^3CH_2(sym)$ stretching band as a function of T_s i.e. duration to which benzene carbon was sonicated. Solid dots represent experimentally observed points, while solid line represents fitted gaussian distribution.

Energy Dispersive Spectrometric (EDS) studies reveal that except 4.5 h sonicated sample, all the samples contain good

amount of oxygen (6–14%) along with carbon. Hydrogen one can not detected using EDS. This strongly corroborates the results of our FTIR studies that some oxygen containing functional groups are attached to the periphery of the carbon network. In case of 4.5 h sonicated sample oxygen content dwindles to 0.5%. Absence of any metallic contaminant is also evident.

Experimental

Hydrogenated amorphous carbon was prepared by burning A.R. grade benzene in a spirit lamp. The pyrolysis product was collected in a clean and polished metal plate by holding it just above the flame. a-C:H so prepared was dispersed in ethanol and sonicated for 0.166 h, 1.5 h, 2 h, 2.5 h, 3 h and 4.5 h in a Eyela ultrasonic bath model 60 watt AVIOC. Eyela, generating 28 kHz ultrasonic waves. The temperature of the ultrasonic bath was kept at 25 °C by adding ice time to time, so that the effect of temperature does not interfere with that of sonication. Transmission electron micrographs and electron diffraction diagrams of each dispersed samples were recorded in a JEOL electron microscope model No. JEM2011. Ethanol was evaporated out from each sample and subsequently FTIR spectra of the dried mass was recorded in a NICOLET FTIR spectrophotometer, model No. IR MAGNA 750, in absorbance mode with 4 cm⁻¹ resolution. Prior to that 50 scans were co-added. Energy dispersive spectrometric (EDS) studies of the dried mass were carried out in a JEOL scanning electron microscope, model No. JSM 6700F.

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